

INGLIZ YOSHLARI DISKURSIDA FATIK MULOQOT BIRLIKLARINING IJTIMOIY VA LINGVISTIK FUNKSIYALARI

Qodirova Xolidaxon Ulug'bek qizi

Farg'ona davlat universiteti 2-kurs doktoranti

qodirovaxolidaxon1999@gmail.com

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz yoshlari kundalik hayotda foydalanadigan fatik muloqot vositalarining kommunikatsion vazifalari tadqiq etiladi. Shuningdek, ularning ijtimoiy hamda lingvistik ahamiyatini yoritib berishga harakat qilinadi. Metadologik manba sifatida Corpus of London teenage language (COLT) va zamonaviy raqamli muloqot ko'rinishlaridan parchalar tanlab olindi. Empirik tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, fatik birliklar muloqotning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, yoshlar nutqiy etiketida milliy qiyofani aks ettiruvchi elementlardan biri bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz yoshlari nutqi, nutqiy etiket, fatik elementlar, lingvopragmatik tahlil, COLT korpusi.

Annotation: In this article, the communicative functions of phatic means used by English youth in everyday life are investigated. In addition, an attempt has been made to reveal their social and linguistic significance. Fragments from the Corpus of London Teenage Language (COLT), as well as examples of modern digital communication, were selected as a methodological basis. Based on the results of empirical analysis, it has been established that phatic expressions are an integral part of communication and act as elements of speech etiquette reflecting national identity in youth discourse.

Keywords: discourse of English youth, communicative etiquette, phatic elements, linguopragmatic analysis, corpus Corpus of London Teenage Language (COLT).

Ingliz jamiyatida muloqotning o'ziga xos komponentlaridan biri small talk hisoblanadi. U nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki ijtimoiy-madaniy norma ham sanaladi. Small talk tabiati jihatidan fatik muloqot bo'lib, uning asosiy funksiyasi axborot almashish emas, balki suhbatdoshlar orasida ijtimoiy aloqa o'rnatish va uni mustahkamlash bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Fatik muloqot tushunchasi ilk marta tilshunos olim Bronislaw Malinowski tomonidan 1923-yilda fanga olib kirilgan [Malinowski,1923].

Inglizlar fatik muloqot chog'ida ob-havo haqida suhbatni boshlashi eng keng tarqalgan holat bo'lib, unga odatiy hol sifatida qaraladi. Mashhur antropolog Keyt Fox bu haqida quydagicha ta'riflaydi: “When two Englishmen meet, their first talk is of the weather” (Qachonki ikki ingliz uchrashib qolganda, ular suhbatni ob-havodan boshlaydilar) [Fox,K 2004]. Ushbu small talk tematikasi juda ham keng tus olgani sababli ushbu suhbat janri “weather-speak” deb ham nomlanadi. Aksariyat kishilar bunday suhbat mavzusining mashhurligining sababi Britaniya ob-havosining tez-tez o'zgaruvchanligi bilan bog'lashsada, aslida bunga sabab ob-havo mavzusi kommunikativ aloqani boshlash va davom ettirish uchun juda ham qulayligidadir.

Masalan, suhbatdosh haqida hech qanday ma'lumotga ega bo'lmaganda, turli sharoitlarda insonlar bilan bir muddat yonma-yon turib qolganda: navbatda yoki jamoat transportlarda weather speak – ob-havo haqidagi small talk kommunikativ noqulaylikni bartaraf etish hamda pauzalarni to'ldirish uchun xizmat qiladi.

Ingliz yoshlari diskursida fatik elementlarni faol harakatini kuzatish mumkin. Yoshlar kommunikativ aloqani boshlash jarayonida qisqartmalar yoki qisqa iboralardan keng foydalanadilar. Bu kabilarga “hey”, “what's up?”, “innit?”, “yeah”, “right”, “okay” kabi birliklarni misol qilib ko'rsatish mumkin.

- Wicked, innit! They just gonna analyse like length of words and that.
- Hey! How was your weekend?
- Hey! It was cool. Yours?
- Hi! Long time no see?
- What's up?

Laver ta'kidlagandek fatik muloqot birikmalarini asosan suhbatning kirish hamda yakuniy qismlarida uchratish mumkin.

- Wagwan? You good? (What is going on? iborasining qisqartmasi)
- You okay?
- You all right there?
- Hiya!
- It is freezing, innit?
- Dead humid today
- Gotta go, see ya.
- Laters
- Catch you later.

Yoshlar orasidagi kommunikativ holatlarda fatik birikmalarning ishtiroki yuzasidan olib borilgan empirik tahlillar shuni ko'rsatdiki, suhbat boshida ishlatilgan kirish yoki yakunlovchi iboralar yoshlarning bir-biriga bo'lgan ijtimoiy yaqinligi hamda hamjihatligining pragmatik ifodasidir [Stenström, A.-B., & Jørgensen, A. M. 2008]. Muloqotni boshlovchi “Hey”, “What's up?”, “You alright” ifodalari aslida suhbatdoshning kayfiyati yoki hol-ahvolini so'rash uchun emas, balki bo'lajak aloqaga tayyorlovchi vosita sifatida qo'llaniladi.

Xayrlashuv ma'nosida nutqda faol harakatlanuvchi “See ya”, “Catch you later”, “Bye”, “I'm off” kabi leksik birliklar suhbatga keskin yakun yasashni oldini oladi va bu jarayonni yanada tabiiylashtiradi.

Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish mumkinki, ingliz yoshlar muloqotida fatik birliklar suhbat boshlash va asosiy mazmunga ko'chishda ko'prik vazifasini bajaradi. Garchi

bu kabi birikmalar qisqa va norasmiy leksikaga boy bo'lsada, nutq ishtirokchilari o'rtasidagi birdamlik va tabiiylikni ta'min etadi.

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